

**THE GLOBAL OUTLOOK OF MULTICULTURAL PSYCHOLOGICAL
COUNSELING RESEARCH: BIBLIOMETRIC AND SCIENTIFIC MAPPING
ANALYSIS (1983-2025)**

**ÇOK KÜLTÜRLÜ PSİKOLOJİK DANIŞMA ARAŞTIRMALARININ KÜRESEL
GÖRÜNÜMÜ: BİBLİYOMETRİK VE BİLİMSEL HARİTALAMA ANALİZİ (1983-2025)**

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to examine the historical development, conceptual transformation, and scientific structure dynamics of multicultural psychological counseling literature, utilizing a large dataset comprising 4,306 articles spanning the period 1983-2025. Bibliometric analyses were conducted to examine annual publication growth, the most productive journals, author institutional distributions, citation performance, and scientific impact. The results indicate that production in the field increased rapidly after 1997 and that a limited number of journals and US-based institutions largely dominate the literature. Thematic analyses show that studies initially focused on cultural awareness, ethnic identity, and demographic groups; over time, they shifted to practical aspects such as professional competence, measurement, supervision, and counselor training; and most recently, they have turned to themes focused on social change, such as social justice, structural inequality, cultural humility, and inclusiveness. This transformation reveals that multicultural psychological counseling has evolved into a deeper and more ethical discipline that aims not only to recognize individual cultural differences but also to identify, critique, and transform social inequalities. The study presents recommendations based on the current literature, specifically that the existing literature's structure needs to be reorganized, researchers from diverse geographical and cultural contexts should be included in the process, and interdisciplinary approaches should be strengthened.

Keywords: Multicultural counseling, cultural humility, competence, psychological counselor, counseling candidates, bibliometric analysis

ÖZET

Bu çalışma amacı, 1983-2025 dönemini kapsayan 4.306 makaleyi içeren geniş bir veri seti kullanarak, çokkültürlü psikolojik danışma literatürünün tarihsel gelişimini, kavramsal dönüşümünü ve bilimsel yapı dinamiklerinin belirlenmesidir. Bibliyometrik analizler ışığında yıllık yayın artışı, en üretken dergiler, yazar-kurum dağılımları, atıf performansı ve bilimsel etki analizleri gerçekleştirilmiştir. Elde edilen sonuçlar, alandaki üretimin 1997'den sonra hızla arttığını; literatürün büyük kısmının sınırlı sayıdaki dergiler ve ABD merkezli kurumlar tarafından domine edildiğini işaret etmektedir. Tematik analizler; başlangıçta kültürel

farkındalık, etnik kimlik ve demografik gruplar üzerine odaklanan çalışmaların; zamanla mesleki yeterlik, ölçme, süpervizyon ve danışman eğitimi gibi pratik yönler; en son olarak ise sosyal adalet, yapısal eşitsizlik, kültürel tevazu ve kapsayıcılık gibi toplumsal değişim odaklı temalara yöneldiğini göstermektedir. Bu dönüşüm, çok kültürlü psikolojik danışmanın yalnızca bireysel kültürel farklılıkları tanımaya değil; toplumsal yapıdaki eşitsizlikleri fark etmeye, eleştirmeye ve dönüştürmeye yönelik daha derin ve etik bir disiplin hâline geldiğini ortaya koymaktadır. Çalışma, literatürdeki mevcut baskının yapının kırılması, farklı coğrafi ve kültürel bağlamlardan gelen araştırmacıların sürece dâhil edilmesi ve disiplinlerarası yaklaşımların güçlendirilmesi gerektiği özelinde öneriler sunulmuştur.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Çokkültürlü psikolojik danışma, kültürel tevazu, yeterlik, psikolojik danışman, danışman adayları, bibliyometrik analiz

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of culture is one of the fundamental concepts in the social sciences. It has been the subject of numerous definitions, shaped by a deep accumulation of knowledge within both historical and social contexts. According to Tylor, who is considered the first researcher to define culture systematically, culture is the totality of knowledge, beliefs, values, art, morals, traditions, customs, and other abilities and habits acquired by individuals as members of society. This definition approaches culture not only as a behavioral pattern but also as the cornerstone of social transmission. Güvenç (2011) emphasizes the historical depth of the concept, stating that the concept of culture was first used by the famous thinker Voltaire in the context of the formation, development, and refinement of human intelligence. Similarly, the Turkish Language Association defines culture as the sum of material and spiritual values produced by societies throughout history and transmitted from one generation to the next. Kağıtçıbaşı (2000) evaluates culture as a whole, comprising learned behaviors, a system of symbols specific to society, and the sharing of meaning. The common conclusion drawn from these definitions is that culture is a complex and multidimensional concept that encompasses both the material and spiritual aspects of human life, serving to give meaning to a broad spectrum ranging from individual behavior to social structure (Aydın, 2014; Özer, 2014). In this context, multiculturalism has become an important concept that refers to the coexistence of different cultures within the same sociopolitical sphere, their mutual interaction, and the recognition of this diversity. Çelik (2008) evaluates multiculturalism as a broad umbrella concept that encompasses political and social arrangements related to the coexistence of different cultures within specific boundaries. Taylor (1996) argues, on the other hand, that multiculturalism is not only a state of coexistence but also an ethical approach that requires the acceptance and appreciation of differences. The APA (2002) defines multiculturalism as awareness of language, religion, race, ethnicity, disability, social class, gender, and other variables related to culture, placing the concept within a broad psychosocial framework. Therefore, multiculturalism has become an indispensable reference point for understanding both social cohesion and individual behavior patterns.

1.1. Transition from Multiculturalism to Psychological Counseling Approaches

The increasing heterogeneity of societies, the sharing of the same social space by different ethnic and cultural groups, and the resulting diversification of psychological needs have made multiculturalism an important subject of study in the field of psychology. The constructivist approach, which developed particularly under the influence of postmodern thought, argues that an individual's reality is shaped by the cultural context in which they

live. Therefore, individual experiences gain meaning within a cultural framework (Corey, 2005). The constructivist perspective emphasizes that the worldviews of individuals with different cultural structures cannot be ignored in psychological counseling processes and that counseling approaches must be adapted to this cultural context (Kararımak, 2016). In this context, multicultural psychological counseling is a need that emerged in response to criticisms that traditional counseling theories cannot fully address individual and cultural diversity. In particular, the civil rights movement, the struggle for racial justice, and demands for social equality that rose in the United States in the 1960s and 1970s paved the way for a fundamental transformation in the field of psychological counseling. During this period, non-white groups expressed that the counseling services offered to them did not reflect their own cultural values and were even shaped by Eurocentric norms (Helms, 1990; Sue & Sue, 1972). These criticisms revealed that psychological counseling must be sensitive not only to individual psychological processes but also to the cultural context in which they occur. Pedersen (1991) defined multicultural psychological counseling as the “fourth force” after psychoanalytic, cognitive-behavioral, and humanistic approaches, noting that this approach is more of a framework guiding the entire field of counseling than a theory. Sue and Torino (2005) defined multicultural counseling as a process that requires understanding the client’s cultural characteristics, developing appropriate intervention skills, and working with cultural awareness at both the individual and societal levels. Multicultural psychological counseling is also viewed as an approach that requires counselors to be aware of their own values and biases, recognize cultural differences between themselves and their clients, and center the client’s cultural identity at the heart of the counseling process. Therefore, multiculturalism is not merely a sociological phenomenon but has become a paradigm that directly shapes psychological counseling practices.

1.2. Multicultural Counseling Competencies and Theoretical Models

The systematic approach to multicultural psychological counseling requires the definition and structuring of counselors’ abilities to respond to cultural diversity. In this context, multicultural psychological counseling competencies were first defined in three key areas in a report submitted to the American Psychological Association by D.W. Sue and colleagues (1992): beliefs/attitudes/awareness, knowledge, and skills. This model has since become one of the most fundamental reference points in the multicultural counseling literature. The first area, awareness, requires the counselor to be aware of their own cultural values, biases, and communication style. The counselor’s understanding of how their own identity affects the counseling process is a fundamental prerequisite for being sensitive to the client’s cultural identity. The knowledge dimension refers to the counselor’s theoretical and practical knowledge of topics such as the historical experiences of cultural groups, communication styles, and processes of oppression and discrimination. The skill dimension encompasses the counselor’s development of appropriate techniques, interventions, and guidance strategies to work effectively with clients from diverse cultural backgrounds. This competency model has been expanded by many researchers in subsequent years, giving rise to various cross-cultural counseling models (Arredondo et al., 1996; Atkinson et al., 1993; Helms, 1990). Research indicates that counselors, particularly those new to the profession, often struggle when working with culturally diverse clients due to factors such as racial bias, limited cultural knowledge, and inadequate skills (Ancis & Sanchez-Hucles, 2000; Holcomb-McCoy & Myers, 1999). These findings have supported the inclusion of cultural competence as a fundamental component of counseling education. Indeed, multicultural counseling courses have been incorporated into counseling education programs in the US and many other countries. Training that develops students’ cultural awareness, allows them to examine their

values critically, and provides them with experiences in cross-cultural interaction has become widespread (Bektaş, 2006). In addition, studies conducted in Turkey also show that multicultural counseling competencies are related not only to theoretical knowledge but also to psychosocial characteristics such as cultural awareness, cultural sensitivity, cognitive flexibility, and cultural intelligence (Aydın, 2014; Buyruk et al., 2018; Demirel, 2016). These findings reveal that cultural competencies have a multidimensional structure and that individuals need to understand their own cultural identity, appreciate the cultures of others, and effectively manage cultural differences.

1.3. The Present Study

In the Turkish context, multicultural psychological counseling practices have experienced significant growth, particularly over the past twenty years. In societies such as Turkey, where cultural diversity is strongly felt within the social structure, it is not possible to conduct the psychological counseling process independently of the cultural context. For this reason, academics have often emphasized the need to incorporate multicultural counseling courses into undergraduate programs in psychological counseling (Kağnıcı, 2011; Kararımak, 2008). It has been stated that these courses should not be limited to providing theoretical knowledge, but should also include developing awareness of cultural diversity, helping students recognize their own value systems, assessing the impact of cultural differences in communication with clients, and integrating culturally appropriate techniques into the counseling process (Erdur-Fırıncı, 2007; Korkut, 2007). Research indicates that multicultural counseling competencies are developed not only through knowledge-based courses but also through intercultural interactions, practical training, and experiences that enable counseling candidates to examine their own cultural identities critically. For example, it has been found that contact with individuals from different cultures plays a decisive role in the development of multicultural competencies; that the perception of cultural competence increases as the level of ethnocentrism decreases; and that characteristics such as cognitive flexibility, cultural intelligence, and cultural sensitivity are critical for multicultural counseling (Buyruk Genç Yüksel Şahin, 2018; Demirel, 2016). This situation demonstrates that multicultural psychological counseling is a holistic competency area that encompasses both personal development and professional skills, going beyond a knowledge-based approach. These contexts demonstrate that multicultural psychological counseling is becoming increasingly important from both theoretical and educational perspectives. However, a review of the literature reveals that there is no comprehensive bibliometric evaluation of the volume, orientation, thematic development, and intellectual structure of studies on multicultural psychological counseling. This research aims to fill this gap by analyzing 4,306 studies published between 1983 and 2025 to reveal the scientific evolution, conceptual orientations, and future research areas of the field of multicultural psychological counseling. Based on this, the research questions were determined as follows:

1. What is the distribution of scientific output and publication trends over the years regarding the concept of multicultural psychological counseling?
2. Which authors, institutions, and countries contribute most to the field, and how is the productivity level of these actors distributed?
3. What are the prominent conceptual themes, keyword clusters, and trending topics over the years in multicultural psychological counseling literature?
4. How is the structure of the field's literature shaped in terms of common citation networks, author collaboration patterns, and scientific interaction networks?

5. In an interdisciplinary context, how is the contribution of multicultural psychological counseling literature to application areas such as psychology, education, social work, health, and counseling distributed?

2. METHOD

2.1. Research Design

In this study, a bibliometric mapping approach combining performance analysis and scientific mapping techniques has been adopted to systematically examine scientific production in the field of multicultural psychological counseling. Bibliometrics is a quantitative research technique that analyzes the written outputs of scientific studies in a specific field, using mathematical and statistical methods, to identify their dimensions, structure, and changes (Al, & Tonta, 2004). During the research process, “performance analysis,” which reveals publication trends in the literature using numerical data, and “scientific mapping,” which visualizes the conceptual structure of the field, were employed in conjunction. The study aimed to track the changes over time and current trends of the subject matter using unbiased indicators (Karagöz, & Koç Ardiç, 2019). Furthermore, this design is based on the methodological framework proposed by Zupic and Cater (2015), which is accepted as the international standard for bibliometric research. In this context, the study includes the following stages: (a) data collection, (b) data cleaning, (c) conducting analyses, and (d) network-based visualization of findings.

2.2. Procedur

The criteria for selecting studies in the analysis are: the publication must focus on multicultural psychological counseling and multicultural counseling, it must be indexed in the Web of Science (WoS) database, and it must have been published between 1983 and 2025. Within this scope, the keywords “multicultural psychological counseling” and “multicultural counseling” were searched in WoS, and irrelevant results were excluded. Only works meeting the specified criteria were included in the dataset. There are two methods for creating bibliometric datasets in analyses (Zupic, & Cater, 2015). The first method adopts a source-focused approach, rather than a topic-focused one, specifically focusing on one or more targeted journals and including works published in these media within the scope of the analysis. The other method, frequently adopted in topic-focused research, involves conducting a comprehensive search using keywords or concept sets defined in relevant databases and filtering the resulting literature pool according to specific criteria.

2.3. Search Strategy, Inclusion Criteria, and Data Collection

In this study, a topic-focused search strategy was applied in the Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection database to comprehensively examine academic production in the field of multicultural psychological counseling. The query was performed in the WoS advanced search module via topic search (TS) using the following Boolean expression: TS = (“multicultural counseling” OR “multicultural psychological counseling” OR “multicultural counsell” OR “cross-cultural counseling”). This search was structured to cover the title (TI), abstract (AB), author keywords (AK), and Keywords Plus fields to ensure that the literature was captured broadly and sensitively (Donthu et al., 2021). The scope of the study included only articles indexed by WoS and published between 1983 and 2025 that focused on multicultural psychological counseling or multicultural counseling themes. Conversely,

publications based on education, sociology, and anthropology in non-relevant fields, documents other than articles (such as book chapters, conference proceedings, editorial material, short notes, and letters), non-English publications, and records not classified as “articles” in the dataset were excluded. The publication pool obtained in line with these criteria was re-evaluated in terms of scientific integrity and subject compatibility.

The data collection process involved examining 4,306 academic studies retrieved from the WoS database through the defined search strategy. First, all records were exported in the “Full Record and Cited References” format, suitable for bibliometric analysis. The files were then downloaded in “Plain Text” format and configured for the Bibliometrix analysis environment (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017). The obtained publications underwent a detailed preliminary review in line with subject coherence and research objectives; records that did not meet the specified criteria were filtered out, and only studies representing the evolutionary development of multicultural psychological counseling literature were retained in the dataset. Thus, a reliable and homogeneous dataset was created, enabling a comprehensive examination of the conceptual and structural transformation of the field within a broad time perspective from 1983 to 2025.

2.4. Data Analysis

The data analysis process for this study involved examining 4,306 academic publications retrieved from the Web of Science (WoS) database using the keywords “multicultural counseling” and “multicultural psychological counseling.” Publications filtered according to the specified inclusion and exclusion criteria were downloaded in BibTeX format, transferred to the R Studio environment, and analyzed using the bibliometrix package (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017). Before commencing the analysis, comprehensive data cleaning was conducted. Studies with weak relevance to the topic were excluded, spelling differences in author and institution names were standardized, duplicate records were removed, and semantically similar keywords were grouped under a single heading. Bibliometrix’s metaTagExtraction and cleanAuthors functions were used during the data cleaning process. The study applied not only basic descriptive statistics related to performance indicators but also network-based relational analyses. Accordingly, annual scientific production, the production performance of sources over time, the most relevant journals, the most productive authors, authors’ productivity curves by year, the most cited documents, country scientific production, countries’ citation performance, and the most influential institutions were analyzed. Additionally, co-citation, co-word, and author collaboration networks were visualized; thematic maps, trend topic analyses, and three-field plot outputs were examined. The Louvain community detection algorithm and normalized co-occurrence coefficient were used to visualize the network-based analyses (Waltman et al., 2010). These analyses comprehensively revealed the historical development, conceptual transformation, and current research trends in the field of multicultural psychological counseling.

3. FINDINGS

This study presents a bibliometric analysis of research in the field of multicultural psychological counseling. The analysis categorizes and presents the findings obtained by publication year and journal, as well as the characteristics of authors and citations, institutions, and countries producing publications related to the subject, and the most frequently used concepts in the literature. The study highlights findings that show scientific

production in the field is geographically concentrated in a specific center, while also shedding light on the transformation of research topics over time.

3.1. Distribution of studies by publication year and journal

The findings of the analysis conducted to determine the annual scientific productivity of the studies are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Annual Scientific Production

When examining the annual scientific production graph in Figure 1, it is evident that the first studies in the field commenced in 1967; however, the number of publications remained at very low levels until the early 1990s. Although there was a partial upturn after 1991, the most significant increase in the literature occurred from 1997 onwards. In the following years, scientific production fluctuated, with significant increases in 2006, 2011, and 2015. After the decline in 2017, the rate of increase gained momentum again, and between 2019 and 2024, the number of articles reached its highest level, representing the most intensive period in the literature. After determining the change over the years, the production of sources over time was examined, and the findings are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Production of Sources Over Time

Figure 2 shows the productivity of the sources that contributed most to the field over the years. When examining the development of these sources, it becomes clear that the Journal of Multicultural Counseling and Development, particularly since 1997, stands out from other sources and has become the most productive. This journal is closely followed by “Counseling Psychologist,” which began to rise in the early 2000s and has shown a marked growth curve, especially after 2009. The “Journal of Counseling and Development,” which is directly related to the subject, has been publishing regularly in the field since the early 1990s, but ranks third in terms of total number of articles due to its slower growth rate compared to the others. The overall picture shows that over the last 20 years, the core journals have continuously increased their publication volume in the field, dominating the literature. To determine which publications supported the observed quantitative increase over the years, the

development of sources over time was analyzed, and the findings are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Most Relevant Sources

Figure 3 presents the top 10 academic sources most frequently cited in the field. Examining this table, which ranks journals by number of publications, reveals that the “Journal of Multicultural Counseling and Development” is the most prolific source with 159 articles. This journal is followed by “Counseling Psychologist,” with 154 publications, and “Journal of Counseling and Development,” with 129 publications. The fact that the number of publications in the other journals on the list is below 75 indicates that academic production on the subject is concentrated mainly around these three leading journals.

3.2. Authors Working on the Research Topic and Citation Distribution

The production of sources over time was examined, followed by a review of authors working on the subject under investigation and an analysis of the distribution of citations. The authors’ production processes over time were investigated, and the findings are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Most Relevant Authors

Figure 4 presents the ranking of authors who have produced the most publications in the field of multicultural psychological counseling. When examining author productivity, Owen Jesse tops the list with 25 articles and is by far the most prolific researcher. This author is followed by Constantine M.G. with 17 publications and Tao Karen W. with 13 publications. These names are followed by a group of researchers, including Arthur Nancy, Davis Don E., and Drinane Joanna M., each with 10 publications. The fact that the number of publications by authors at the top of the list is significantly higher than that of others shows that specific leading names dominate production in the field. Following the publication outlets, the performance of researchers who shape the literature was examined, and the findings are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Authors' Production Over Time

Figure 5 presents the publication performance over time and the duration of activity in the literature for the most productive authors. Examining the graph, it is evident that Constantine M.G. pioneered the early period of the field by regularly publishing works between 1996 and 2007; however, his productivity subsequently ceased. In contrast, names such as Hays Danica G. (2005-2025) and Tao Karen W. (2008-2025) stand out for their long-term contributions spread over a wider time frame. In particular, the work of researchers such as Owen Jesse and Davis Don E., which intensified after 2012 and has continued uninterrupted to the present day, shows that this group of authors has shaped the current dynamics of the field. Furthermore, the representation of Deblaere Cirleen's 2019 publications with dark colors and large circle diameters indicates that the author's work during this period had a strong impact on the literature and received high citations. Findings regarding collaboration among authors are presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Collaboration Network

Figure 6 presents a collaboration network reflecting the culture of joint work among authors. Upon examining the network structure, it is evident that numerous isolated clusters are working independently and disconnected from one another, rather than forming an integrated communication network that encompasses all researchers in the field. In particular, while the large group centered around Owen Jesse and Tao Karen W. (blue cluster) and Arthur Nancy and his team (purple cluster) demonstrate strong collaboration within themselves, there is no connection between these groups. This fragmented appearance suggests that scientific production in the field of multicultural psychological counseling is conducted by small and closed research teams rather than a broad-based network.

3.3. Distribution Of Broadcasting Organizations And Countries

In addition to individual productivity, a network map of authors has been created to reveal researchers' communication patterns with one another and their collaborative culture. Analyses of the connections between publishing organizations and countries are presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Country Scientific Production

Figure 7 shows the geographical distribution of scientific production in the field by country. Examining the color intensities on the map, it can be seen that the darkest blue tone represents the United States (US) and dominates the literature on its own. The US is followed by European countries such as China, Canada, the United Kingdom, Australia, and Spain, which have lower publication densities. The fact that Africa, South America (except Brazil), and a large part of Asia appear in gray or very light blue tones on the map reveals that academic production in this field does not show global homogeneity; on the contrary, it shows that studies largely follow a North American and Western-centric development trajectory. To determine the extent to which the geographical distribution of publications is reflected in academic impact, the citation performance of countries was compared, and the findings are presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Most Cited Countries

Figure 8 compares the academic impact levels of countries based on the total number of citations received by the publications they produce. The table reveals a striking result: The United States stands out in the literature with a total of 28,582 citations. The fact that South Korea, ranked second on the list, and China, ranked third, remain at a symbolic level, with 146 and 51 citations, respectively, highlights the enormous gap between the two countries.

These data demonstrate that the theoretical knowledge base and reference sources in the field of multicultural psychological counseling are predominantly centered in the US. At the same time, the influence of other countries in the literature remains relatively limited. When these country-based results are examined at the institutional level, the distribution of universities contributing most to the field is presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Most Relevant Affiliations

Figure 9 presents the ranking of institutions that have made the most significant contributions to the field of multicultural counseling. Examining the institutional distribution, Capella University ranks first with 54 articles, closely followed by Walden University with 51 articles. Western Michigan University follows these two leading institutions with 46 publications. The production volume of the top three universities on the list clearly stands out compared to Columbia University (32) in fourth place and the institutions that follow, indicating that scientific production in the field is heavily concentrated in these three centers. Furthermore, the fact that all institutions on the list are based in the United States confirms the US hegemony identified in previous country-based analyses at the institutional level.

3.4. Most Cited Studies, Concepts Used, and Their Distribution

After examining the productivity levels of various higher education institutions, the transition from the structural characteristics of the field to its conceptual framework was made, and the most frequently cited studies that form the theoretical foundations of the literature were examined. The section on the most commonly used terms related to the researched topic and their distribution was followed by a presentation of trend topics and a thematic map showing the density and centrality of concepts. Findings were presented in Figure 10 by examining the studies that form the theoretical foundations of the literature and are most frequently cited.

multicultural and counseling nodes, represents the field’s professional education, competency standards, and social justice advocacy dimensions, centered around the concepts of competence, training, supervision, and social justice. The red cluster, located on the left side and dominated by the concept of “students,” with concepts such as “identity,” “development,” “international,” and “racial,” shows that research focuses more on university students, identity development, and cultural variables. This dual structure demonstrates that the field of multicultural psychological counseling aims at both theoretical and professional development, on the one hand. On the other hand, it has an applied character that examines developmental processes in specific populations. Following the primary sources, a trend analysis was conducted to show the changes in the main research topics in the literature over the years, and the findings are presented in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Trend Topics

Figure 12 presents a trend analysis illustrating the evolution of research topics over time. Examining the temporal progression of the topics reveals that the late 1980s and early 1990s saw a predominance of concepts such as “cross-cultural counseling,” “ethnicity,” and “Mexican Americans,” with this period focusing more on basic definitions and specific demographic groups. From the mid-2000s to 2015, the increased frequency of concepts such as “multicultural competence,” “supervision,” and “scale development” indicates that the field’s focus shifted to professional standardization, education, and measurement tools. In recent years (2020-2025), the direction of the literature has shifted significantly; the concepts of “structural racism,” “inclusion,” “social justice,” and “cultural humility” have emerged as the most current trends. This situation proves that multicultural psychological counseling practices today have evolved beyond discussions of technical competence into a more systemic process that questions social structures and prioritizes inclusivity and social justice.

Figure 13. Thematic Map

Figure 13 shows the density and centrality of concepts on the thematic map. This map is divided into four main sections, each named according to the arrangement of different themes:

- **Motor Themes:** This area, which contains themes with high centrality and high density values, is where the concept of multicultural counseling competence is located. This indicates that the topic of multicultural counseling competence is both strongly intertwined with other topics in the field and has reached a high level of development within itself, serving as the driving force behind the literature.
- **Niche Themes:** Concepts such as students, American, and college are located in this region. These themes show that studies on university students and the American context exhibit developed structures within themselves, but their relationships with other main themes in the literature remain weaker. Therefore, these concepts are explored in depth in specific areas but are situated in a specialized position rather than at the center of the general literature.
- **Emerging or Declining Themes:** This section, which contains themes with low centrality and low intensity, includes concepts such as study, school, and perceptions. These themes represent topics that have gained less ground in the development process, remain at a weak level, or form the periphery of the field.
- **Core Themes:** This region is reserved for core themes with high centrality but relatively low density values. This area includes key concepts such as culture, education, and counseling. These terms are indispensable building blocks that form the general theoretical foundation of the field, are linked to most studies, and upon which research is built.

In summary, the concept of multicultural counseling competence stands out as the most developed and central theme of the field. In contrast, the concepts of education and counseling form the fundamental basis of the field. Sample-focused concepts, such as students and college, on the other hand, have developed in a more isolated and niche area.

4. Discussion

This study comprehensively evaluates the historical development, conceptual orientations, and structural patterns of scientific production in the field of multicultural counseling within a bibliometric framework. The findings reveal that the field has gained significant momentum, particularly over the past twenty years, transforming into an expanding research network at both theoretical and applied levels. When publication trends, collaboration patterns, and thematic clusters are considered together, it is evident that multicultural psychological counseling has increasingly assumed a central disciplinary position and has become a strategic area in the global psychological counseling literature. The scientific production in the field of multicultural psychological counseling, which gained significant momentum after 1997 and peaked during the 2019-2024 period, is supported not only qualitatively but also quantitatively, as evidenced by bibliometric data. The productivity of journals that have become the publication centers of the field has directly driven this increase. Journals such as the *Journal of Multicultural Counseling and Development*, *The Counseling Psychologist*, and the *Journal of Counseling and Development* are among the most prolific sources of publications in this field. A bibliometric study conducted by Roziqi (2023) revealed that publication trends related to multicultural counseling competence are concentrated in specific journals and among certain authors. The study revealed that a small number of publications and researchers dominate keywords and citation patterns. This finding confirms that production in the field of multicultural psychological counseling is centralized and that scientific diversity has become dependent on certain sources, as was also evident in our analysis. Similarly, Fadilah and colleagues' (2025) study, analyzing 316 articles in the Scopus database, emphasizes the dominance of Western countries and specific journals in the field of multicultural counseling. Furthermore, this study reports that the field has shifted from technical applications to social justice-based approaches since 2000 and that publications have increased in parallel with this thematic transition. These trends suggest that scientific production in the field has not only deepened quantitatively but also conceptually. However, the concentration of most production around a few central journals may lead to both the monopolization of knowledge production and the limited reflection of alternative perspectives. In this context, a more balanced and globally participatory publication environment could both increase theoretical diversity and strengthen cultural sensitivity in practice.

Scientific output in the field of multicultural psychological counseling exhibits a structure where a small number of pioneering researchers stand out, and these names largely determine the direction of the field. Authors such as Jesse Owen, M.G. Constantine, and Karen W. Tao are prominent in the literature, with a notable number of publications and high citation counts. However, bibliometric data reveal that despite this high productivity, collaboration structures among authors are quite limited and fragmented. A unified and integrated collaboration network has not formed across the field; instead, isolated clusters have emerged, shaped around independent, closed, and often two- or three-person groups. This situation contrasts with the interdisciplinary and intercultural nature of multicultural counseling, which limits the circulation of knowledge among broader communities and hinders the development of pluralistic perspectives. The lack of broad academic synergy can constrain both innovation and global impact. Therefore, encouraging more open, interdisciplinary, and intercultural collaborations could make scientific productivity more inclusive by increasing the field's methodological diversity and theoretical depth.

Bibliometric analyses conducted in the field of multicultural psychological counseling reveal that scientific production is largely centered in the US and that this situation creates a serious imbalance in global knowledge production. Fadilah and colleagues (2025), analyzing

316 studies in the Scopus database, noted that the vast majority of publications in this field originate from Western countries, with the United States leading by a wide margin in terms of publication volume and impact. The representation of Asian and Global South countries is quite limited, highlighting the issue of scientific hegemony. Similarly, Kılavuz (2023), in his extensive bibliometric analysis of the field of multicultural education, emphasizes that the majority of the 1,300 publications examined originated in the US and that the most productive universities are also located in this country. This concentration is led by institutions such as Capella University, Walden University, and Western Michigan University. Sumargono et al. (2024) also state that the US leads in institutional and individual productivity in this field, while global collaborations remain insufficient. These findings demonstrate that knowledge production in a field that should be global and inclusive by its very nature, such as multicultural counseling, is confined to a single-centered and homogeneous structure. Therefore, encouraging participation from diverse regions, especially those in the Global South, integrating local knowledge systems, and promoting cross-cultural collaborations are of great importance for a more balanced scientific ecosystem.

4.1. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study provides a comprehensive overview of the historical development, production centers, influential actors, and conceptual transformations in the field of multicultural psychological counseling, based on an analysis of bibliometric data. The findings reveal that scientific production gained momentum, especially after 1997, peaked in the 2019-2024 period, and was largely concentrated in a limited number of journals, such as *The Journal of Multicultural Counseling and Development*, *The Counseling Psychologist*, and *The Journal of Counseling and Development*. Productivity in the field was found to be concentrated around a small number of pioneering authors such as Jesse Owen, M.G. Constantine, and Karen W. Tao; in contrast, collaboration networks remained fragmented and limited to closed structures. Geographical analyses showed that the United States was the clear leader in terms of both publications and citations, with institutions such as Capella and Walden standing out. At the conceptual level, it has been determined that the field is not limited to cultural awareness; in recent years, it has shifted towards a more systemic, critical, and justice-based orientation through concepts such as “structural racism,” “social justice,” and “cultural humility.” In light of these findings, it is recommended that institutional and geographical centralization in the field be reduced, international collaborations strengthened, support for researchers in the Global South be provided, and local cultures be more fully integrated into the counseling literature. Furthermore, counseling competencies focused on social justice should be disseminated not only at the theoretical level but also in field applications; these themes should be placed at the center of academic curricula. In this way, multicultural psychological counseling can become an ethical and transformative field of practice that can effectively address not only individual diversity but also structural inequalities.

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